

A Novel Online Cross-Section Collapsing Scheme Based on Fixed-Source Iteration for Microreactor Analysis

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803684

ABSTRACT

Accurate resonance self-shielding treatment under an ultra-fine group structure is essential for full spectrum problems, yet direct ultra-fine group transport calculations remain computationally prohibitive for whole-core problems. To address this challenge, this paper proposes a novel online cross-section collapsing scheme based on fixed-source iteration. The method efficiently generates on-the-fly weighting spectra by approximating the eigenvalue problem as a fixed-source problem under a flat fission source assumption. Furthermore, to capture anisotropic scattering effects, a high-order flux moment approximation is introduced, which reconstructs moments using the scalar flux and macroscopic total cross-section.

The proposed method is verified and validated using the Empire microreactor benchmark problem. Sensitivity analyses on fuel assemblies confirm the validity of the introduced approximations, showing negligible eigenvalue deviations relative to rigorous transport solutions. Whole-core simulations demonstrate excellent agreement with continuous-energy Monte Carlo reference solutions: eigenvalue differences are maintained within 230 pcm, control drum worth deviations are limited to -16 pcm, and pin power distributions match within a maximum error of 1.2% (RMS error 0.42%). These results confirm that the proposed scheme effectively balances computational efficiency with high-fidelity accuracy for advanced reactor analysis.

Keywords: Online cross section collapsing, fixed-source iteration, resonance self-shielding, Empire microreactor

1. INTRODUCTION

To meet the requirements of neutronics analysis for advanced reactors with complex spectral characteristics, we have previously developed a lattice physics code under an ultra-fine group framework [1]. This code serves as the primary tool for generating few-group cross-sections for microreactor designs at the assembly level.

However, due to significant neutron leakage and strong spectral interactions between neighboring assemblies in microreactor designs, the core environmental effect plays a critical role in few-group cross-section generation [2]. To capture these effects accurately, few-group cross-sections should be generated online (on-the-fly) during whole-core calculations.

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While extending the geometric modeling from the assembly to the whole-core scale is straightforward, the computational burden becomes prohibitive when solving the eigenvalue problem using ultra-fine group cross-sections derived from resonance calculations. To overcome this efficiency bottleneck, this work introduces a novel acceleration scheme.

Specifically, we propose an online cross-section collapsing scheme based on fixed-source iteration. To balance accuracy and efficiency, the time-consuming eigenvalue problem is approximated as a fixed-source problem under the flat fission source assumption. This formulation allows for the efficient estimation of ultra-fine group fluxes, including high-order flux moments. These fluxes are subsequently utilized to condense cross-sections from the ultra-fine structure into a coarse-group structure for the final whole-core eigenvalue calculation. The proposed method is verified using the Empire microreactor benchmark problem [3], with sensitivity analysis performed on fuel assembly problems and performance assessment on 2D core configurations.

2. METHOD

2.1. Construction of the Fixed Source Problem

The steady-state multi-group neutron transport equation is expressed as:

$$\nabla\varphi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r})\varphi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{\chi_g(\mathbf{r})}{k_{eff}} \sum_{g'=1}^G v\Sigma_{f,g'}(\mathbf{r})\phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,g'\rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r})\phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (1)$$

The terms on the RHS of Eq. (1) represent the fission source and the scattering source, respectively. In the standard source iteration method, the fission source is updated based on the flux from the previous iteration, while the scattering source is updated within inner iterations.

For cross-section collapsing, the accuracy of the flux shape (spectrum) is paramount, whereas the absolute magnitude is of secondary importance. To decouple the spectrum calculation from the source iteration, a flat fission source approximation is adopted, assuming a uniform source distribution within fuel regions:

$$\frac{1}{k_{eff}} \sum_{g'=1}^G v\Sigma_{f,g'}(\mathbf{r})\phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \equiv 1 \quad (2)$$

Substituting Eq. (2) into Eq. (1) reduces the eigenvalue problem to a fixed source problem (FSP):

$$\nabla\varphi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r})\varphi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \chi_g(\mathbf{r}) + \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,g'\rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r})\phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3), high-energy neutrons are generated exclusively through the fission term χ_g , while up-scattering is confined to the thermal energy region. Consequently, the solution of Eq. (3) closely resembles that of a pure slowing-down equation. This characteristic facilitates a direct energy sweep from high to low groups, thereby significantly enhancing computational efficiency compared to solving the original eigenvalue problem.

2.2. Approximation of High Order Flux Moments

For large systems, NJOY code approximates the high order flux moments by employing the narrow resonance (NR) and B_N approximations within Bondarenko model [4]. This relationship establishes an inverse dependence on the total cross-section, expressed as:

$$\phi_l(E) = \frac{W_l(E)}{[\sigma_t(E)]^{l+1}} \rightarrow \phi_l(E) = \frac{\phi_0(E)}{[\sigma_t(E)]^l} \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (4), $W_l(E)$ represents the energy-dependent weighting function derived from the Bondarenko iteration in the offline library generation stage, which accounts for the smooth part of the neutron spectrum.

Adopting a similar methodology, this work reconstructs the high order flux moments directly from the scalar flux obtained in the previous step and the macroscopic total cross section. The l 'th flux moment is formulated as:

$$\phi_{g,l} = \frac{\phi_{g,0}}{[\Sigma_{t,g}]^l} \quad (5)$$

2.3. Generation of Coarse Group Cross Sections

The fundamental principle governing the cross section collapsing process is the conservation of reaction rates. The purpose of equivalence techniques like SPH factors is to ensure that the coarse-group reaction rates match a reference distribution. However, in this work, the ultra-fine group weighting spectra are derived from an approximate fixed-source problem rather than from a reference transport solution. Using SPH factors to force equivalence to an approximation is logically inconsistent and could lead to numerical instability. The condensation scheme differs depending on the physical dependency of the parameters.

The fission spectrum describes the energy distribution of secondary neutrons emitted from fission reactions and is generally considered independent of the incident neutron energy. Consequently, it is directly collapsed by summing the fine-group contributions within each coarse group, without flux weighting, as expressed in Eq. (6):

$$\chi_{cg} = \sum_{g \in cg} \chi_g \quad (6)$$

In contrast, interaction cross sections are inherently dependent on the energy of the incident neutron. Therefore, they are collapsed using flux-weighting schemes to preserve reaction rates. Specifically, angle-independent cross-sections (where subscript x represents total, fission, and nu-fission reactions) are weighted by the scalar flux, as shown in Eq. (7). The high-order scattering matrices are condensed using the corresponding high-order flux moments, as formulated in Eq. (8):

$$\Sigma_{x,cg} = \frac{\sum_{g \in cg} \Sigma_{x,g} \phi_{g,0}}{\sum_{g \in cg} \phi_{g,0}} \quad (7)$$

$$\Sigma_{s,l,cg \rightarrow cg'} = \frac{\sum_{g \in cg} \sum_{g' \in cg'} \Sigma_{s,l,g \rightarrow g'} \phi_{g,l}}{\sum_{g \in cg} \phi_{g,l}} \quad (8)$$

2.4. Workflow of the Online Cross Sections Collapsing

The comprehensive workflow of the proposed online cross-section collapsing scheme is illustrated in Figure 1, comprising the following steps:

1. **Offline Library Generation.** Initially, a Master Library is generated offline. The NJOY nuclear data processing system, managed by a dedicated Python suite, processes raw ENDF/B data to produce isotopic multi-group libraries under the ultra-fine group structure.
2. **Online Resonance Calculation.** Upon receiving the main input parameters (geometry, material compositions, etc.), the code performs an online resonance calculation to determine the macroscopic cross-sections under the ultra-fine group (FG) structure.
3. **Fixed-Source Transport Calculation.** This is the core step of the proposed method (Transport Cal. 1). The eigenvalue problem is reduced to a fixed-source problem based on the flat fission source assumption. Solving this yields the approximated scalar flux, which is subsequently used to reconstruct the high-order (HO) flux moments. The fixed-source problem (Eq. 3) is solved on the same 2D whole-core geometry as the final eigenvalue calculation. This allows the method to capture the spatial-dependent spectral effects on-the-fly.

4. Cross-Section Condensation. Utilizing the fine-group macroscopic cross-sections and the calculated flux moments, cross-section collapsing is performed. This generates effective macroscopic cross-sections under the coarse-group (CG) structure, strictly adhering to the principle of reaction rate conservation.
5. Whole-Core Eigenvalue Calculation: Finally, the condensed coarse-group cross-sections serve as input for the rigorous whole-core transport simulation (Transport Cal. 2) to determine the system's effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) and power distribution.

Figure 1. Workflow of the online cross section collapsing scheme

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Problem Description

The proposed method is verified against the Empire microreactor benchmark problem [3]. The core consists of 18 fuel assemblies surrounded by a radial beryllium reflector. Reactivity control is managed by 12 rotating control drums (CDs) located within the reflector blocks, while a central void region is reserved for a safety shutdown rod. Each fuel assembly comprises a stainless-steel monolith housing 60 fuel rods, 61 heat pipes, and 96 moderator pins (yttrium hydride) arranged on a triangular pitch.

The configurations of the unit fuel assembly and the full core are illustrated in Figure 2. Detailed geometric parameters and material specifications are available in Ref. [3]. For modeling simplicity, a hexagonal boundary condition is applied to the core periphery. All numerical calculations utilize ENDF/B-VII.0 data, with all materials maintained at a uniform temperature of 300 K.

Figure 2. Empire micro reactor fuel assembly (left) and whole core (right)

3.2. Analysis of the Online Cross Section Collapsing Method

To validate the approximations introduced in the method, specifically the flat fission source assumption and the high-order flux moment approximation, a sensitivity analysis was conducted on the Empire fuel assembly.

3.2.1. Validity of Flat Fission Source and Group Structure

In this part, the impact of the coarse group structure and the number of source iterations on accuracy is investigated. Six representative fuel pins and four coarse group structures, as depicted in Figure 3, were selected to analyze the macroscopic cross-section errors.

Figure 3. 30° slice of single assembly with indexed regions (left) and coarse group structures (right)

The maximum relative error is adopted as the evaluation metric, calculated using Eq. (9):

$$\text{Maximum Error} = \max_{cg} \left(\frac{\Sigma_{appro.} - \Sigma_{conv.}}{\Sigma_{conv.}} \times 100\% \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\Sigma_{conv.}$ and $\Sigma_{appro.}$ represent the cross section collapsed using the converged flux and the approximate flux, respectively.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the maximum errors of total cross sections remain below 0.2% across all pins and coarse group structures under the flat fission source assumption (Iteration 0). Performing a single fission source update (Iteration 1) further reduces these errors to below 0.05%. Generally, under the same iteration step, the error magnitude decreases as the number of energy groups increases.

Figure 4. Maximum error of total cross section under Iteration 0 (left) and Iteration 1 (right)

Table 1 summarizes the eigenvalues calculated using the collapsed cross-sections across various iteration steps and group structures. The results demonstrate that the eigenvalue stabilizes immediately; the deviation between Iteration 0 and the converged results is negligible (maximum 4 pcm). This confirms that the flat fission source assumption is sufficiently accurate for generating weighting spectra.

Among the tested structures (23, 47, 70, and 172 groups), the 70-group structure yields the highest accuracy (deviation of ~ 7 pcm), likely due to error cancellation effects. Consequently, the 70-group structure is adopted for subsequent analyses

Table 1 Eigenvalue and responding error under different coarse group structures

Iteration times	Eigenvalue (Deviation / pcm)			
	23-group	47-group	70-group	172-group
0	1.21004 (46)	1.20972 (14)	1.20966 (7)	1.20923 (-35)
1	1.21007 (48)	1.20973 (14)	1.20966 (7)	1.20923 (-35)
2	1.21008 (49)	1.20973 (14)	1.20966 (7)	1.20923 (-35)
4	1.21008 (50)	1.20973 (14)	1.20966 (7)	1.20923 (-35)
5	1.21008 (50)	1.20973 (14)	1.20966 (8)	1.20923 (-35)
6	1.21008 (50)	1.20972 (14)	1.20966 (8)	1.20923 (-35)
7	1.21008 (50)	1.20972 (14)	1.20966 (8)	1.20923 (-35)
8	1.21009 (50)	1.20972 (14)	1.20966 (8)	1.20923 (-35)
9	1.21009 (50)	1.20972 (14)	1.20966 (8)	1.20923 (-35)
10	1.21009 (50)	1.20972 (14)	1.20966 (8)	1.20923 (-35)

* Reference eigenvalue obtained under the ultra-fine group structure is 1.20958.

3.2.2. Validation of High-Order Flux Moment Approximation

This section evaluates the feasibility of approximating high-order flux moments to account for anisotropic scattering effects during the cross-section condensation process. The impact of utilizing different weighting spectra for high-order scattering matrices on eigenvalue accuracy is analyzed. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Eigenvalue and corresponding error under different weighting sources

Case ID	Group Number	Weighting Source	Eigenvalue	Deviation / pcm
1	FG	-	1.21850	-
2	CG	Accuracy Pn Flux	1.21855	+5
3	CG	Accuracy P0 Flux Approximate Pn Flux	1.21855	+5
4	CG	Approximate P0 Flux Approximate Pn Flux	1.21870	+20

Case 1 serves as the reference, representing the rigorous Fine-Group (FG) transport calculation with P2 scattering. Case 2 represents the Coarse-Group (CG) calculation where cross-sections are condensed using accurate high-order moments explicitly derived from the FG solution. The negligible deviation of +5 pcm in Case 2 confirms that the selected CG structure effectively preserves the spectral information.

The proposed method approximates high-order flux moments utilizing the scalar flux and the macroscopic total cross-section. When this approximation is applied specifically to the high-order scattering matrices (Case 3: Accurate P0 / Approximate Pn), the result is identical to the rigorous Case 2 (+5 pcm). Furthermore, even when both the scalar flux and high-order moments are approximated (Case 4: Approximate P0 / Approximate Pn), the deviation remains minimal at +20 pcm. These results

demonstrate that the reconstructed high-order moments provide a highly accurate alternative to the rigorous angular flux moments, effectively capturing anisotropic scattering effects with negligible loss in precision.

3.3. Verification on the Empire Core Problem

In this part, the validation is extended to the 2D whole-core problem, considering scenarios with CDs rotated both in and out. Leveraging the core's symmetry, calculations for both the fixed-source problem and the eigenvalue problem are performed on a 1/6-core geometry, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. 2D one-sixth core configuration with (left) CDs rotated in and rotated out(right)

Consistent with the assembly analysis, the eigenvalue calculations employ the 70-group structure derived in the previous section. Anisotropic scattering effects are treated up to the second order (P2). Due to the prohibitive computational cost of solving the ultra-fine group transport equation for the whole core, reference solutions are provided by the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code OpenMC [5].

Table 3 compares the eigenvalues obtained from OpenMC and the proposed method in this work. The results demonstrate good agreement, with eigenvalue deviations remaining within 230 pcm for both CD-in and CD-out configurations. Furthermore, the control drum reactivity worth predicted by the proposed method aligns closely with the reference, showing a discrepancy of only -16 pcm.

Table 3 Eigenvalues from OpenMC and online XSs generation

CD State	OpenMC	Online XSs Generation	Deviation / pcm
CD out	1.17281	1.17490	209
CD in	1.14676	1.14901	225
CD worth (pcm)	2605	2589	-16

* The standard deviations of OpenMC eigenvalues are less than 0.00003.

Detailed computational costs for the 2D Empire core, specifically for the control-drum-in scenario, are presented in Table 4. The initial fixed-source calculation and cross-section collapsing are completed in 1363 s and 2734 s, respectively. The subsequent coarse-group eigenvalue calculation is performed in just 1005 s, highlighting the method's ability to bypass the prohibitive computational burden inherent in conventional ultra-fine group transport simulations.

Table 4 Computational cost in control drums rotated in case

Content	Group Number	Scattering Order	Time / s
Fixed Source Calculation	FG	P0	1363
Cross Sections Collapsing	FG->CG	P2	2734
Whole Core Calculation	CG	P2	1005

Figure 7 illustrates the relative error of the pin power distribution between the proposed method and the OpenMC reference. The power distributions calculated by the proposed method show excellent agreement with the reference, with maximum relative errors within 1.2% for both cases. The Root Mean Square (RMS) errors are consistently below 0.42%. Spatially, the errors exhibit a distinct pattern: fuel

pins located in the assembly centers show lower errors due to the relatively uniform neutron environment. Conversely, slightly larger errors are observed for fuel pins near the periphery, specifically those adjacent to the central void region and the radial reflector, where spectral gradients are more pronounced.

Figure 7. Relative error of pin powers for the 2D Empire cores with CDs rotated in (left) or out (right)

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a novel online cross-section collapsing scheme based on fixed-source iteration, employing flat fission source and high-order flux moment approximations to efficiently generate on-the-fly weighting spectra. Sensitivity analysis on the Empire fuel assembly confirms the validity of these approximations, yielding negligible eigenvalue deviations relative to rigorous transport solutions. Validation against OpenMC for the whole-core problem demonstrates high accuracy, with eigenvalue differences within 230 pcm, control drum worth deviation of -16 pcm, and pin power distributions matching within 1.2% (maximum error) and 0.42% (RMS error). These results confirm that the proposed scheme effectively balances computational efficiency with high-fidelity accuracy for microreactor analysis.

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